

A Novel A-IMC Ge-GST ePCM Cell for Edge AI Applications on 28nm FD-SOI Platform

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Abstract—A new Ge-GST embedded PCM cell architecture, optimized for Deep Neural Network (DNN) acceleration, is presented. Its integration flow is discussed, and its dimensions are optimized through TCAD simulations. An extensive electrical characterization of conductance levels is performed to assess analog programming and level stability over time and temperature. Simulations of a large DNN, based on the gathered data, demonstrate the superior performance of the optimized cell when compared with standard Wall structure ePCM. Finally, functionality on a large statistic is demonstrated with the validation of a test-vehicle showing good process yield. Silicon implementation of a Neural Network (NN) proves the excellent A-IMC characteristics of this new architecture.

I. INTRODUCTION

Analog In-Memory Computing (A-IMC) has become a trending topic due to the promise of high speed and energy efficiency compared to conventional Neural Processing Unit for edge AI [1]. Among the resistive memory devices proposed for such use [2], embedded Phase Change Memory (ePCM) is one of the most mature technologies for embedded applications. High speed, with read operation in the ns time scale, and small dimensions, with possibility for further scaling, are key attributes of these devices [3]. Intermediate Reset States (IRS), necessary for A-IMC applications, are typically obtained with small volumes of amorphous material. The crystallization of such small amorphous volume could represent a limitation for technology adoption and was never deeply investigated in literature. It will be shown how, through cell architecture engineering and utilization of Ge-rich GST (Ge-GST) as active material, it is possible to guarantee thermal stability of IRS at high operating temperatures. In this work, the development and validation of an optimized ePCM architecture, the Rheostatic cell [4,5], based on previously developed 28nm ePCM cell [3], is presented. This structure is the best-in-class among ePCM devices for A-IMC applications for the low programming currents and small footprint of $0.036\mu\text{m}^2$. The latter is limited by the choice to use a MOS selector rather than a BJT. The choice of MOS device as a selector leads to better current control resulting in a better analog programming response. The use of Ge-GST alloy combined with the new architecture ensures high device retention. This means both resilience from state crystallization at high temperatures and low drift coefficient for intermediate states. Process integration details, TCAD simulations and electrical characterizations will be shown. Experimental results will be used to simulate a ResNet32 Deep Neural Network (DNN) architecture showing high accuracy performances over long periods of time for

different temperatures. Finally, a dedicated test-vehicle will be presented showing excellent wafer integration capabilities. The implementation of a small NN on such test vehicle confirms the expected high performances of the Rheostatic architecture in A-IMC applications.

II. RHEOSTATIC CELL

Fig.1 shows the structures of Wall (a) and Rheostatic (b) ePCM architectures. In the latter a thin layer of conductive material, called lamina, is added between the heater and the GST active material and extends along the full cell length. The purpose of this added element is to decouple read and write current paths during the device operation [4] thus avoiding conduction through the unstable and noisy amorphous state. In the wall architecture, the cells on the same Bit-Line (BL) share a continuous chalcogenide strip. To integrate the Rheostatic cell, a confinement in all directions is done to be able to obtain a fully amorphous cell state avoiding sneak paths through the lamina layer. A customized etch step perpendicular to the BL was developed to interrupt the continuous lamina/chalcogenide strip along the BL. The integration flow was further modified from [3] by adding tuned dielectric fillings and CMP steps to achieve a fully confined cell with the wanted morphology. Fig.2 highlights the main process steps of the new architecture. The integration flow was adapted from the 28nm ePCM technology described in [3]. Uniform deposition of the active stack composed of lamina layer, GST and Top Electrode (TE), is done. Then a new etch step, followed by cell sealing and filling with dielectrics, is introduced to segment the device in the direction parallel to the Word-Line (WL). The TE of the cell is then exposed through CMP, and an additional metallic material is deposited on top of it. Then patterning of the BL is done, like in the unconfined architecture, through the BL mask. At this point, the added metallic layer is defined in lines, connecting confined cells along the same BL. Sealing and filling dielectrics are then deposited to insulate each device. Integration then continues as in [3] with a top connection through dedicated vias to upper metal levels. Fig.3 shows a Dark-Field Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (DF-STEM) image of the final device. Extensive TCAD studies, shown in Fig.4, were done according to our previously developed model [6], to optimize the cell dimensions. Fig.5 shows excellent agreement between measured and simulated current-voltage (a) and programming current-conductance level (b) curves for the Wall and Rheostatic cells with various geometries. Fig.6 shows the characterization of the activation energy of conduction (E_a) of the two architectures. Cells were programmed with a Program & Verify (P&V) algorithm at the same starting level and then annealed at 85°C for 5h. Electrical measurements to extract E_a , were done at lower temperatures, between 25°C and 65°C, to

avoid further conductance drift evolution [7]. The lower values of E_a obtained for the Rheostatic structure demonstrate correct working behaviour of the lamina layer. To assess the temperature stability of IRS high temperature bakes between 200°C and 230°C were performed on a cell programmed at 20 μ S as shown in Fig.7 (a). This conductance value was chosen as reference maximum conductance value to be used in an A-IMC application to reduce power consumption. It also represents the worst-case scenario for crystallization having the smallest amorphous dome in the conductance range considered (least resistive state). Extraction of the activation energy for crystallization (E_{ax}) is shown in Fig.7 (b) and results to a value of $E_{ax} = 2.65$ eV leading to a projected retention of 10 years at 143°C.

III. NEURAL NETWORK SIMULATIONS

To evaluate the architectures performance in DNN applications, a dedicated measurement routine was designed as shown in Fig.8. A batch of Wall and Rheostatic devices were first programmed through P&V algorithm along a wide range of conductance levels, ranging from 1 μ S to 50 μ S, well beyond the 20 μ S level set by power consumption considerations. A readout step was performed at room temperature with 10k reads to characterize the cell after programming. Different temperature bakes (ranging from 25°C to 125°C) at cumulated times (spanning until one week from the program pulse) were done to stimulate drift and its temperature acceleration. At the end of each bake the cell would go through another room temperature readout step with 10k reads. In doing so it was possible to decouple the characterization of the drift and noise contributions. Drift is extracted by averaging the different readouts for each cell and studying the time evolution at different temperatures. Noise by analysing the spread of readout values after each evolution. The results of this characterization at the different temperatures considered are shown in Fig.9, 10, 11. The Rheostatic cell has a much lower median drift (Fig.9) in the whole conductance range and comparable drift dispersion (Fig.10). Read noise, shown in Fig.11 with the characterization done after 7 days at 125°C, has comparable results for both architectures. To study the impact of the cell characteristics on the accuracy of large DNN, simulations of a ResNet32 Neural Network with CIFAR10 dataset were done using [8]. The devices were assumed to have a conductance between 0.1 and 20 μ S and be programmed with a 1s delayed verify P&V algorithm as in [9]. Tab.I reports the most important assumptions done during modeling. Cell characteristics used in the simulations for drift, noise and temperature activation are shown in Fig.6, 9, 10, 11. NN accuracy evaluation was repeated 20 times to properly account for device and system variability (e.g. weights variations due to conductance program noise and device characteristics variability). Fig.12 (a) shows the calculated accuracy evolution for the network up to 10 years at room temperature. Fig.12 (b) shows the time necessary for a 20% drop in accuracy from baseline for each implementation at different temperatures. It is clear how the Rheostatic architecture gives an advantage of at least 2 orders of magnitude with respect to Wall for all the temperatures. For the first time in literature, the effect of conductance changes caused by different read operating temperatures on the accuracy of an analog implemented NN are presented in Fig.13. Also on this regard, the Rheostatic

structure is the best performing option thanks to its lower temperature sensitivity (E_a). Tab.II reports a comparison with other State of the Art PCM based A-IMC accelerators.

IV. TEST VEHICLE

A dedicated test-vehicle [13] with A-IMC capabilities was developed in two versions with both Wall and Rheostatic ePCM cells. Here the Rheostatic cell version is considered to evaluate the integration quality by array yield tests. This demonstrator is equipped with 4M cells, 11-bit ADC and 8-bit DAC for signal conversion and a dedicated drift compensation module to compensate the median drift behavior [13]. Device functionality was tested by programming the test chip in a digital 0/1 state equivalent to fully amorphous/crystalline chalcogenide. Fig.14 (a) shows the resulting distributions being well separated for all dice considered, confirming a correct cell integration on a large statistic. Fig.14 (b) shows good yield on wafer maps. For precise analog conductance programming on test-chip, a P&V algo was developed. Fig.15 shows the ideal vs real conductance programming characteristics collected. The programming noise on the developed test vehicle is uniformly distributed between less than $\pm 0.8\mu$ S of the target value. This value was used to compute the simulations in Fig.12 to have a coherent accuracy prediction. Finally, a Neural Network with 7680 weights, trained to recognize MNIST digits was implemented on chip. Accuracy was evaluated by performing 22000 inferences on different images and evaluating the rate of correct recognition. This procedure was repeated after 1-hour bakes at different temperatures ranging from 25°C to 125°C. Accuracy results are shown in Fig.16. The network is clearly not impacted from drift instabilities in the considered time-temperature range in coherence with the simulation results.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The superior capabilities of the Rheostatic ePCM cell as a device for A-IMC applications are clearly demonstrated. It significantly outperforms the Wall architecture in terms of time and temperature stability. DNN simulations based on cell electrical characterizations reveal highly promising results for applications in a variety of markets. Demonstration of the integration quality and DNN acceleration characteristics were demonstrated on a test-vehicle. This works demonstrates the feasibility of A-IMC accelerators based on Rheostatic Ge-rich GST ePCM cells and paves the way for larger Neural Network implementation in the test-vehicle.

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Fig. 1. Schematic structure of Wall (a) and Rheostatic (b) ePCM cell architecture. The sneak path through the lamina layer decouples the read and write path of the Rheostatic cell. Resistance read in intermediate reset states will be proportional to the amorphous dome size thus creating a linear programming curve characteristic.

Fig. 2. Process flow for Rheostatic cell integration. Labels x.1 and x.2 represents the cross section along WL and BL respectively. a) represents the memory stack after segmentation along BL [3]. b) is after CMP to expose Top Electrode. c) Further metallic material deposition. d) patterning of the cells to create a fully confined structure. e) dielectrics fillings. On the bottom short description of the process flow.

Fig. 3. Dark Field Scanning Transition Electron Microscopy (DF-STEM) image of the Rheostatic cell. All the different elements are highlighted with labels.

Fig. 4. TCAD simulations of the Rheostatic cell for increasing simulated programming pulses ($I_{prog,1} < I_{prog,2} < I_{prog,3}$). On the first row the phase of GST material on the second row the corresponding current.

Fig. 5. Current voltage characteristics of the Rheostatic ePCM cell for different GST widths. Modulating the dimensions of the cell the slope of the curve in the on region (from approximately 1V on) changes. (a) Conductance vs programming current characteristics. Different shades of blue represent GST widths coherently with (b). Dots are data, lines are TCAD simulations.

Fig. 6. In a) behavior of Activation energy for conduction (E_a extracted from Arrhenius dependence as reported on top) vs target conductance after a P&V algorithm (before bake). In b) Arrhenius plot of 2 cells after 5h bake at 85°C, programmed at t_0 at the same target conductance.

Fig. 7. In a) conductance evolution for different stress temperatures of a $20\mu S$ state of a Rheostatic Ge-rich GST ePCM cell. In b) Arrhenius plot extracted from a). The resulting activation energy for crystallization is 2.65eV. The expected retention time of the cell is of 10 years at 143°C.

Fig. 8. Schematic representation of the measurement procedure for drift and noise characterization of the two different ePCM structures. First groups of cells are programmed through P&V at different conductance values. Then the devices enter a cycle of readout phase and temperature evolution. In the readout phase each cell is read 10k times to extract the read noise characteristic. A bake at high temperature is then applied to accelerate drift. The cycle repeats until a cumulated bake time of 7 days is reached. In this way it is possible to characterize drift and noise independently from each other.

Fig. 9 Median drift behavior of different conductance states for Wall (a), and Rheostatic (b), ePCM cell architectures. Different stress temperatures are represented by different shades from 25°C (light hue) to 125°C (dark hue).

Fig. 10 Cell to cell spread of drift coefficient for different conductance states for Wall (a), and Rheostatic (b), ePCM cell architectures. Different stress temperatures are represented by different shades from 25°C (light hue) to 125°C (dark hue).

Fig. 11 Read noise for Wall (in red) and Rheostatic (in blue) ePCM cell architecture after 7 days at 125°C.

Tab. I Neural Network simulation parameters.

MVM Crossbar	Size: 512x512	4-pass: Digital Sum
ADC	Resolution: 10 bits	Output noise: 4%
	Non idealities: none considered	
DAC	Resolution: 8 bits	Output noise: 0%
Conductance Mapping	Differential 2 cells	$G_{max} = 20\mu S$ $G_{min} = 0.1\mu S$
	Program Noise equal to Fig.15	
Others	Global Drift Comp. ON	IR-drop OFF

Fig. 12 Accuracy over time at 25°C of a simulated ResNet32 DNN implemented with Wall and Rheostatic cell. In b) time necessary for a 20% accuracy drop from baseline of the network implemented with each ePCM structure vs temperature evolution. Rheostatic cell has a longer retention with respect to Wall of least two decades

Fig. 13 Simulated accuracy of a ResNet32 NN for different read temperatures. Only the median value was considered due to the additional contribution to dispersion caused by the wafer level analysis.

Tab. II Comparison with State-of-the-Art PCM NN accelerators

	Memory Tech.	Tech. node	Physical cell size	Bottom Electrode contact	Weight	Inference accuracy
[10]	Wall Ge-GST PCM	90nm	0.19 μm^2	<10nm	2T2R	MVM only
[11]	Projected Doped GST PCM	14nm	N.A.	>25nm	8T4R	ResNet34 in ImageNet 71.4% (simulation result)
[12]	Mushroom PCM	14nm	N.A.	>25nm	8T4R	ResNet9 on CIFAR10 85.6% (hardware result)
This Work	Rheostatic Ge-GST PCM	28nm	0.036μm^2	<10nm	2T2R	ResNet32 on CIFAR10 91% (simulation result)

BINNING TABLE

(12) Register Fail	(11) SRAM Fail
(2) Bad Array	(0) GOOD

Fig. 14. (a) Test-vehicle distributions of Set (crystalline) and Reset (amorphous) state at the wafer scale. Each line represents one die on wafer. All dice are functional and there is clear separation between the two states confirming a correct process integration. (b) Wafer maps of different test chips show good process yield. There are no morphological heterogeneities highlighting the strength of the new process flow adopted for the Rheostatic cell.

Fig. 15. Characterization of real vs ideal conductance values programmed through P&V algorithm in the test vehicle. In a) scale is log-log while in b) is linear for both axes. Program noise is bounded between $\sim \pm 0.8 \mu S$ in the whole conductance range.

Fig. 16. On the left a photo of the test vehicle used to evaluate NN performances highlighting the dedicated space for A-IMC core and peripheral logic. On the right the resulting NN accuracy of the network implemented on chip after different 1h temperature bakes.